

NEW DISEASE REPORT

First report of soybean dwarf virus in clover species in Ireland

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Soybean dwarf virus (SbDV) was initially described in Japan, causing significant yield loss in soybean (*Glycine max*) in the 1950s. Over the past two decades, the virus has been detected in Europe in various legume species (broad beans, clover and pea), in the Czech Republic, Germany, Finland and most recently in Great Britain. The first report of SbDV in Europe was from Germany in 2007 (Abraham *et al.*, 2007).

In March 2024, plant samples from the margins of a spring barley field in County Kildare (Ireland) were collected to enable characterisation of viruses at the agro-ecological interface. Samples of the most abundant plant species (following the sampling protocol outlined in Bernardo *et al.*, 2017) at five sampling points were freeze-dried, milled, and all species collected from a single sampling point were pooled prior to total RNA extraction. Illumina sequencing (PE 150 bp) was conducted following rRNA depletion and library preparation. Taxonomic profiling was performed with KRAKEN2 (Wood *et al.*, 2019) and viral reads extracted (SRR31213025) and used for *de novo* assembly with megaSPAdes (Nurk *et al.*, 2017). The longest contigs from two sampling points had 96.5–97% sequence identity with SbDV isolate NZ-Y (GenBank Accession No. OR553425). The same viral reads were mapped to OR553436 and a consensus sequence for the Irish isolate was extracted and deposited in GenBank (PQ412811). SbDV was confirmed in the two sampling points using PCR analysis with the strain-specific MDF, MYF and MUR primers (Schneider *et al.*, 2011).

Based on the taxonomic profiling, the most likely SbDV host in the species mixture was white clover (*Trifolium repens*). This was subsequently confirmed by testing the freeze-dried samples of white clover

collected from the field margins prior to pooling and confirming the presence of SbDV with PCR. Furthermore, to obtain a preliminary assessment of prevalence, five white clover samples from two sites in County Kildare, as well as four red clover (*Trifolium pratense*) samples from a site in County Kilkenny, were collected at random. The SbDV Y strain was detected using PCR in three white clover samples from two different sites, and the SbDV D strain was identified in one red clover sample.

This represents the first report of SbDV in Ireland. Given the prevalence and increasing importance of clover to grassland agriculture in Ireland, white and red clover are an abundant potential reservoir of SbDV. Considering that SbDV is transmitted by two aphid species commonly found in Ireland (*Acyrtosiphon pisum* and *Aulacorthum solani*), the potential impact of SbDV on legumes in Ireland, such as clover and broad beans, necessitates monitoring. Furthermore, its presence should be considered when assessing the risks of introducing other legumes, including soya bean varieties adapted for cool environments.

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